

GASTRIC DILATATION VOLVULUS IN A CAT (A PROBLEM ORIENTED APPROACH)

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A 7-years old, Castrated Male, 6.5 Kg, Domestic short hair cat was presented with the primary complaint of persistent abdominal distension, and frothy salivation (since last 24 hours). Serous ocular discharge and “treated previously but remained unresolved mucoid nasal discharge” since past 4 days was the secondary major complaint. Upon clinical assessment, the cat was in mild respiratory distress with asymmetrical abdominal distension, predominantly on the left side. Furthermore, the abdomen was tympanic at percussion. Congested mucous membranes with CRT <1 sec, mild bradycardia (154 bpm) and poor pulse quality were the prominent features of the clinical assessment; this led to the distributive shock although 39° C was normal temperature according to the presentation of this cat. Vocalization with URT and LRT wheezes were accompanied findings assessed during physical examination.

Minimum database for this particular patient showed left shift with bands, lymphocytosis and monocytosis as conspicuous findings in blood count and mild increase in BUN and CREAT in blood chemistry. *Chlamydophila felis* antibody titre was at higher scale which indicated clinical stage of infection. Mild elevation of lactate was a salient marker for shock indication. The cat was initially managed by oxygen-therapy and intravenous administration of Hartmann’s solution (HM) with initial bolus followed by maintenance rate and antibiotics post blood results. A whole body right lateral radiograph revealed intra-abdominal dilated stomach displacing the pylorus dorsally, supported by thicker than normal dilated esophagus and gas filled intestinal loops. A diagnosis of GDV was formulated on the basis of radiographic findings (Fig 1).

To mitigate the symptoms related to mild dyspnoea, decompression of the stomach was performed by rhino-gastric tube of 1.2 mm diameter. Approximately 6 hrs after presentation, exploratory surgery was undertaken. The stomach was found roughly 180° rotated. Very mild haemorrhagic changes without any obvious necrotic properties seen on the fundus side of the stomach. Incisional gastropexy was

performed to fix the stomach with right side abdominal wall to restore its normal position. Rhino-gastric tube feeding started 6 hrs post-surgery with prescription diet a/d slurry. The cat began to ingest food by mouth within 12 hrs postoperatively and was discharged 48 hrs thereafter continued management and further treatment regimen of the *C.felis*. GDV did not recur at the time of writing almost 1.5 years after surgery. Prognosis is favourable if initial shock stage managed well.